

Hypothetical mosaic protein 1 translated from transcript MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071

Putative protein-synthesizing GTPase

-2 (2r→3a) +2 (3a→2r)

mRNA
2,152

MS peptide 24 Se
MS peptide 23 L
Mosaic protein 1

Hypothetical mosaic protein 3 translated from transcript MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461 Putative ribulose-bisphosphate carboxylase (RuBisCo)

MS peptide 100 BWPCPD
MS peptide 98 B
Mosaic protein 3

Supplementary Dataset S5. Three candidate mosaic proteins deduced from chimeric MS peptides. This dataset is an extended version of Figure 1. Mosaic proteins 2 and 3 differ by one amino acid around the -2 PRF site (red-boxed R and K, respectively). The upper portion of each figure depicts a corresponding transcript with ORFs mapped and scaled relative to the whole transcript length. Asterisks represent positions of PRF events. The text in blue describes the PRF value, type, and subtype of each frameshifting event. Interpretation example: -2 (2r→3a) refers to a frameshift with value minus 2 from a refORF in frame 2 (yellow) to an altORF in frame 3 (pink). The green triangle indicates the position of the first in-frame translational start codon (AUG). The complete sequence of each hypothetical mosaic protein is shown at the bottom of corresponding images.